

Paper Chromatography of Some Inert Cobalt (III) Complexes

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R_f values of twenty-nine inert cobalt(III) complexes of varied ionic charge (from +3 to -3) are reported. In 1N ethylamine solution the R_f values gradually increase with decrease of positive ionic charge. A mechanism involving electrostatic nature of adsorption is suggested.

Chromatographic studies on only a few cobalt (III) complexes are described in the literature¹⁻⁶. This communication reports the results of our chromatographic studies on several inert cobalt (III) complexes of different charge type (from +3 to -3). Inert cobalt (III) complexes were used in the present study so as to minimize the possibility of any structural change in the process of chromatographic development.

EXPERIMENTAL

The complexes were prepared according to the published procedures⁷⁻¹⁰. The identity of the synthesized products was established by means of elemental analysis and electronic spectra. The complexes of different ionic charges examined and their R_f values are included in Table I.

Distilled water and 1N aqueous solution of ethylamine were used as developer. This 1N solution of ethylamine was prepared from a 50% commercial ethylamine (E. Merck, Germany). The filter paper used was Whatman Paper No. 1 especially processed for chromatography. A strip of filter paper (5 cm × 45 cm) was used. The samples were studied by descending strip chromatographic methods. The time required for the development was about 3 hrs. The migrated spots on the paper were identified by spraying a 5% solution of sodium sulphide. Sometimes coloured spots were quite visible without spraying sodium sulphide solution. R_f values were measured as the centre of the distance between the front and the end of the spot as suggested by Lacourt, Sommereyns and Wantier¹¹.

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TABLE I

R_f Values of Cobalt (III) Complexes Developed with in Ethylamine Solution

Ionic Charge	Compound	R _f Value
+3	[Co(ophen)Et(BigH) ₂]Cl ₃ ·3.5H ₂ O	0.54
	(Co(dipy)(AMUH) ₂)Cl ₃ ·7H ₂ O	0.57
	[Co(ABiUH)(BigH) ₂]Cl.tartrate·5H ₂ O	0.58
	[Co(APiUH)(BigH) ₂]Cl ₃	0.63
	[Co(dipy)Et(BigH) ₂]Cl ₃ ·2.5H ₂ O	0.63
	[Co(ophen)(AMUH) ₂](CampSO ₃) ₃	0.66
	[Co(BigH)(AEUH) ₂]I ₃	0.65
	[Co(BigH)(AMUH) ₂]I ₃	0.66
	[Co(AMUH)(BigH) ₂](SO ₄) _{1.5} ·3.5H ₂ O	0.67
	[Co(AMUH) ₃](SO ₄) _{1.5}	0.66
	[Co(BigH) ₃](SO ₄) _{1.5} ·3.5H ₂ O	0.69
	[Co(BigH)(en) ₂]SO ₄ ·I	0.69
	[Co(OX)(AAiUH) ₂](OX) _{1.5} ·H ₂ O	0.69
	+2	[Co(gly)(AMUH) ₂]Cl ₂ ·5H ₂ O
[Co(gly)Et(BigH) ₂]SO ₄ ·1.5H ₂ O		0.74
[Co(NH ₃) ₂ (APiU)(APiUH)]I ₂		0.75
+1	<i>Trans</i> [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AMUH) ₂]NO ₂	0.82
	<i>Cis</i> [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (AMUH) ₂]NO ₂	0.79
	<i>Trans</i> [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (ABiUH) ₂]NO ₂ ·8H ₂ O	0.81
	<i>Cis</i> [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (ABiUH) ₂]NO ₂	0.77
	<i>Trans</i> [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (APiUH) ₂]NO ₂ ·2H ₂ O	0.82
	<i>Cis</i> [Co(NO ₂) ₂ (APiUH) ₂]NO ₂	0.78
0	[Co(CN) ₂ (Big)(BigH)]	0.87
	[Co(CN) ₂ (AMU)(AMUH)]	0.86
	[Co(gly) ₃]	0.84
-1	NH ₄ [Co(NO ₂) ₄ (NH ₃) ₂]	0.90
	K[Co(NO ₂) ₄]	0.90
-3	Na ₃ [Co(NO ₂) ₆]	0.97
	K ₃ [Co(NO ₂) ₆]	0.97

Where O-phen = orthophenanthroline; dipy = 2-2'-dipyridyl; en = ethylenediamine; glyH = glycine; OX = oxalate ion; BigH = biguanide; AMUH = 1-amidino-o-methylurea; AEUH = 1-amidino-o-ethylurea; APiUH = 1-amidino-o-isopropylurea; ABiUH = 1-amidino-isobutylurea; AAiUH = 1-amidino-o-isoamylurea; Et(BigH)₂ = ethylenedibiguanide and CampSO₃H = *d*-camphor-10-sulphonic acid.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The different cobalt (III) complexes were developed in both distilled water and ethylamine. The chromatographic patterns of all the complexes in water was diffused from the point of origin to the end. The presence of NaCl or KCl decreased diffusion of spots. In case of tripositive cations it was noticed that R_f values in water were greater than that in ethylamine. The R_f values of the tripositive salts in water medium mostly lie in the range 0.8 to 1.0. When ethylamine was used as developer the tailing of the spots were somewhat less. The lower R_f values in ethylamine are probably due to its much greater basic character.

In case of *tris* (glycinato) cobalt (III) and diammine-tetranitrocobaltate (III) no change in the R_f value on changing the developer (water to ethylamine) was noticed.

If all the complexes are arranged in order of their ionic charges in different groups then a nice sequence in R_f values is noticed (see Table I). The R_f values increase with decrease of positive ionic charge. This suggests the electrostatic nature of adsorption of the complex on paper, and that this electrostatic force on the paper must be negative in nature. This is very reasonable since cellulose contains many ionizable hydrogen atoms which may dissociate with the consequent development of negative charge on the paper. Cationic complexes will thus be more strongly attracted on the paper than the non-electrolytes or anionic complexes, and thus the observed variation in R_f values of the complexes of different charge types can be accounted for.

It can be seen from Table I that the R_f values of *trans* isomer are somewhat higher than those of the *cis* form. Low dipole moment of *trans* isomers may account for higher R_f values than for the *cis* isomers¹².

This study also indicates that the conversion from homochelate *tris* (biguanide) cobalt (III) or *tris* (1-amidino-o-methylurea) cobalt (III) to heterochelates having both the ligands in the coordination zone does not show appreciable change in R_f values. The homochelates $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{AMUH})_3](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ exhibit R_f values 0.69 and 0.66 respectively. Any of the mixed ligand heterochelates formed from the combination of these two ligands also showed almost the same R_f values or intermediate values between the two extremes. This is presumably due to the very similar bulky nature of the two ligands, having very close positions in the spectrochemical series, forming analogous complexes with similar bonding¹³. Recently for some copper (II) heterochelates, Farona, Perry and Kuska have also observed R_f values intermediate between those of the homochelates¹⁴.

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